

A road for the future

JOSÉ PAPI, Secretary General of the International Road Federation - Brussels Programme Centre, on the economics of road transport policy

petrol industry, car insurance companies, etc.), representing almost 8 per cent of the total EU-25 workforce. Road transport is also one of the largest contributors to national budgets. In 2002, the European Commission released a report on vehicle taxation in the EU-15, which indicated that vehicle-related taxes represented up to 10 per cent of the total fiscal income of some EU Member States. Road construction activities themselves also generate economic growth. According to a nation-wide report commissioned by the French Senate in 1995, an investment of €150m in roads creates, on average, 3,240 jobs, of which 1,210 are directly related to the road construction works, while 575 are linked to the activities undertaken prior to the construction, and 660 are directly related to the production of construction materials, in addition to 800 jobs resulting from construction-related investment revenues.

Finally, by contributing to regional cohesion, roads play a prominent role in the geographic distribution of economic growth. Zones with high job densities (over 200 jobs per sq km) are typically located near major road arteries. There are a number of reasons behind this concentration. Industries need to be located where they have a direct and easy access to their suppliers, customers and employees.

This explains why industrial zones are generally located near roads and why roads themselves are so important to regional development (tourism, business location decisions, etc.). At macroeconomic level, an efficient, well-interconnected road network can act as a catalyst in fostering development by creating sustainable, autonomous growth zones, which in turn increase the per capita income in less favoured regions to levels closer to the European average.

The social dimension of road transport

Changing living patterns have also increased the role of roads in such areas as access to employment, education

For too many years the role of road transport in modern economies has been negligently overlooked and substituted by theories advocating the negative effects of such means of transportation.

Today, the argument that roads are the backbone of Europe's socio-economic model is backed by solid empirical evidence and numerous academic studies. Finally we are realising that the wealth of a nation is inexorably interlocked with the presence of a modern and well-maintained transport infrastructure.

In spite of this, the past decade has seen a consistent decline in spending on road infrastructure in the European Union. Often fuelled by ideological arguments, this persisting trend has come at the cost of increased congestion and lower safety levels.

The European Commission, however, can legitimately

point to a number of achievements since 2001, chief amongst which is drastic cuts in pollutant emissions (- 40 per cent) and road fatalities (- 17 per cent), and improved working conditions for the millions employed by the transport sector. It must also accept that it has been less than successful in tackling congestion, revitalising Europe's railways or identifying global solutions to help fund the Trans-European Networks.

Enlargement has given the EU a continental dimension and created more transport corridors, but at the same time stretched the ability of the Community's financial resources to offer basic accessibility to citizens living in central and eastern Europe.

On the supply side, consolidation is taking place at European level in all transport modes, setting the conditions for increased European competition as motorway

operators and haulage firms vie for new markets. Increased investment in research and innovation in areas such as engine technology, intelligent transport systems and infrastructure management are transforming the transport sector into a high-technology industry. As Europe celebrates 50 years of coordinated policy-making, it needs to adopt a fresh vision on transport. Recognising the socio-economic contribution of road transport and listening to the mobility aspirations of millions of motoring citizens is an indispensable first step.

The economic role of road transport

As evidenced by basic economic data, the global economic impact of roads and road transport on our lives is considerable. As many as 16m EU citizens work directly or indirectly for the road sector (automotive suppliers,

and health care. As Europe evolves from the old economy of manufacturing to a service-based knowledge economy, traditional patterns of transport to workplaces are breaking down. While improvements in information and communications technology have helped to make distance less important, the countervailing trend of geographical dispersal of workplaces – in small businesses, rather than large, centrally located concerns that can be efficiently serviced by public transport – has increased the demand for road transport.

In 2004, two thirds of new jobs were created in the suburbs, where roads are often the only means of transportation which can be used for commuting.

In the UK, travel costs are so high that they are considered a significant barrier to post-secondary education. A study released in 2002 by the Social Exclusion Unit revealed that travel costs are the largest expenditure associated with postsecondary education. The study also found that one in every five students had considered dropping out from their studies because of the travel-related cost-burden.

Six per cent of students missed college courses from time to time due to transport costs, and a further six per cent turned down the offer of vocational training or further education on at least one occasion because they were unable to get to the educational establishment offering them a place. Finally, lack of adequate transport can also reduce the opportunity to use medical services, resulting in increased costs to health care providers due to missed appointments and delayed interventions.

Car ownership and freight transport

Car-ownership in the European Union has surged over the past 10 years. In 2003 alone, 13,842,044 new cars were purchased, representing a 25 per cent jump on car sales in 1993, while registrations increased by 13.2 per cent in OECD countries between 1990 and 2005. Passenger transport by road (whether by car or bus), which already represents 92 per cent of total passenger transport, has seen an increase of 12.5 per cent between 1995 and 2002. The demand for road transport originates from different categories of users, ranging from passenger cars & trucks to motorcycles, bicycles and passenger buses, depending on the purpose of travel.

Figures for the United Kingdom suggest that individual car travel is used primarily for shopping, leisure and going to work with an average of 641 car journeys per person every year. In the 19th century, an average European travelled about 20 km a year, while today this figure is 20 km a day. This data explains why access to a car is essential for the majority of people and why car ownership per 1,000 inhabitants has more than doubled since 1970. Roads are the only mode of transport which can provide a door-to-door connection at a competitive price. The average time in Europe for a home-work journey by car is estimated to be 20 minutes. The corresponding figure for public transport is estimated to be

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38 minutes, or almost twice as much.

A recent survey pointed out that road transport is considered by 62 per cent of the population as the most practical mode of transport. If citizens no longer had access to a car, over half of them believe their day-to-day tasks would become more difficult as a result.

The decision to buy a car and to spend a considerable part of the household budget can only be explained by the fact that the economic advantages of using roads (saving money, more efficient use of time, increased comfort and quality of life) outweigh the direct costs of owning and using a car. Nobody has ever forced anybody else to buy a car and use it.

Setting the record straight

The 2nd European Road Congress (Brussels, 6-8 November 2006) offered the perfect setting for stakeholders to analyse and debate the future orientation of road trans-

port policy in Europe. It was broadly agreed that changes in the attitude towards road infrastructure and road transport in general are needed to encourage further growth and foster competitiveness in the sector.

ITS will, in a matter of years, completely revolutionise the way in which the journeys for people and merchandise are planned and undertaken.

A key factor in this change is the implementation of GALILEO, Europe’s satellite navigation programme, which will provide the technological infrastructure needed to further reduce the negative impact of road transport.

The monitoring and management of traffic fluidity will be significantly improved when a great number of cars are equipped with satellite navigation receivers and guidance systems. For example, if the average speed of the cars equipped with GALILEO receivers on a given road sector drops significantly, a control centre can anticipate a traffic jam and suggest that approaching vehicles

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choose a different route. Several studies have concluded that the potential for reducing travel time thanks to the use of ITS could be 10 -20 per cent. Furthermore the increase of the use of such a tool as Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) to finance the road sector has become a priority for a sector where “consumers” have been shown to be willing to pay extra in order to obtain better quality services and infrastructure. Historically there has been a relative under-usage in Europe of PPPs to finance the road sector.

However there is ample evidence that allowing private enterprises to share the cost of building new infrastructure and then providing them with concessions to raise toll-based revenue has led to an improvement in the maintenance level of the road infrastructure itself and generated better services to motorists. Future policy ought to reflect the fact that the private sector wants and needs to be involved to a higher degree in all phases, from design to implementation, of road infrastructure. When taking into consideration progress made to achieve “greener” transportation we can clearly see that thanks to a successful string of emission norms, harmful pollutants from new vehicles are a small fraction of what they were 20 years ago, fleet emissions are being reduced substantially as older vehicles are gradually replaced and CO₂ emissions are set to decrease over the years as more stringent EU norms are implemented.

Quiet contemplation

Traffic noise is another typical area of conflict between individual mobility needs and legitimate societal aspirations for quieter lifestyles. With some 80m EU citizens suffering from unacceptable levels of noise today – much of it caused by the transport sector as a whole and being responsible for €38bn in lost productivity and property value decrease – there is a clear need for Europe to take a driving role in promoting targeted legislation, sharing solutions and achieving a common understanding of the potential for progress in order to reduce the road traffic-related noise level.

In addition, a substantial progress has already been made by the automotive sector itself, which is illustrated by the fact that 12 modern trucks today generate the same noise levels as a single truck manufactured in 1974. Future progress can be expected through new tyre design, quieter engines and silent pavements.

The future will also have to offer more and better solutions to tackle the problem of road safety. In the EU-25, in fact, there are over 40,000 road fatalities every year, with an estimation currently putting the cost of these deaths at 2 per cent of the overall EU GDP.

The tragedy of each and every life prematurely ended on our road network should offer scope for reflection and prompt policy-makers at all levels to take concrete action if they wish to attain the target of halving this number by 2010. **TH**

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